

BUILDING REVISIT INTENTIONS THROUGH DESTINATION TRUST AMONG GENERATION Z TOURISTS IN WEST JAVA PROVINCE, INDONESIA

SUJANA¹, NOVAN YURINDERA², NANDAN LIMAKRISNA³ and
W. HARRY SUSILO⁴

^{1,2,3,4}Faculty of Economics and Business - Universitas Persada Indonesia Y.A.I – Jakarta.

Email: ¹sujana.2366370002@upi-yai.ac.id (*Corresponding Author), ²novan.2366390001@upi-yai.ac.id,

³nandan.lima.krisna@upi-yai.ac.id, ⁴harry.susilo@upi-yai.ac.id

Abstract

This study aims to address and analyze the research gaps in various previous studies and to address the phenomenon where Destination Trust serves as an inconsistent intervening variable that can explain Revisit Intention. These factors motivated this study. This research is a quantitative descriptive study using the Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) analysis method in the LISREL application. The research subjects were Generation Z tourists enrolled in Islamic Higher Education Institutions under the supervision of Kopertais Region 2 West Java and who had visited several halal tourist destinations in West Java in 2024. The population of this study was 451,624 Generation Z tourists, resulting in a sample size of 400. The results of this study indicate that all exogenous variables significantly explain their influence and are positively correlated with the endogenous variables, with the dominant variables being Tourist Experience on Destination Trust and Destination Trust on Revisit Intention. These results are expected to assist management in organizing and maximizing Revisit Intention through Destination Trust.

Keywords: Halal Destination Image, Tourist Experience, Service Quality, Destination Trust, Revisit Intention.

INTRODUCTION AND LITERATURE REVIEW

West Java is an integral part and a key supporter of tourism in Indonesia, boasting the most tourist attractions compared to the other 38 provinces in the country. According to data from Statistics, 2021, West Java boasts the most tourist attractions in Indonesia, with 414 out of a total of 2,563. Specifically, 141 of these attractions are man-made. There are 116 natural attractions, 101 water attractions, 37 amusement parks, 16 cultural attractions, and 3 tourism areas. East Java comes in second with a total of 408 tourist attractions. Central Java follows with 356 tourist attractions. North Maluku was the province with the fewest tourist attractions in 2021, with 5. These include 2 natural attractions, 2 man-made attractions, and 1 cultural attraction.

West Java, a province with a predominantly Muslim population, experienced a 0.03 percent increase from 2021 to 2022. Meanwhile, the Christian and Catholic populations decreased by 0.02 percent and 0.01 percent, respectively. Meanwhile, the population of other religions in West Java remained constant. This population size provides a strong justification for conducting research on halal tourism in West Java. In a province-level region like West Java, where the majority of the population is Muslim, domestic tourists do not need to consider the

halal aspect of a halal tourism area. Halal restaurants and places of worship are relatively easy to find. The opinion expressed by Julina et al. (2021) appears to be true. Meanwhile, according to Suryanto & Kurniati (2020), there are still differing understandings of halal tourism among the community and stakeholders, which can be an obstacle. However, Suryanto & Kurniati (2020) further stated that understanding of halal tourism in Indonesian society remains biased. Indonesians tend to view halal tourism as synonymous with religious tourism.

Halal tourism is an adoption from non-Organization of Islamic Conference (OIC) countries that created halal tourism to accommodate the worship needs of Muslims in non-OIC countries, such as the provision of places of worship and halal restaurants. Meanwhile, Islamic tourism, essentially, is a new interpretation of pilgrimage that elaborates aspects of religious motivation and leisure tourism activities (tourism for relaxation/general tourism), such as a combination of tour packages. Misperceptions of understanding of halal tourism can be one of the obstacles in the development of halal tourism in West Java. Therefore, a common understanding between the government, stakeholders, and the community regarding halal tourism is needed. This is where the role of the National Sharia Council of the Indonesian Ulema Council (DSN MUI) as an institution that produces fatwas (decisions on a matter related to Islamic law) is essential in providing guidelines so that a common understanding of halal tourism in Indonesia is formed. The growth of halal tourism in Indonesia continues to increase every year, however, public understanding of the concept of halal tourism is still relatively low. People in Indonesia still consider halal tourism as something ordinary Nurlatifah (2024) in Julian et al. (2024). Increasing public literacy regarding halal tourism can be an effective tool for promoting the halal industry, such as halal tourism. However, the low level of public literacy regarding Islamic economics in general is a significant obstacle. Literacy regarding halal tourism is not only limited to knowledge, but also includes awareness of the importance of the concepts of halal and haram in choosing tourism products and services (Febrianty & Rulindo, 2024). Many actors are reluctant to implement the concept of halal tourism due to misunderstandings about the word halal. They assume that implementing the halal concept means turning the entire tourist location into a place of worship. In fact, halal tourism actually only ensures the availability of facilities and services that are friendly to Muslim tourists, such as halal restaurants and easily accessible places of worship (Riansyah & Ismail, 2024).

The performance of halal-friendly destinations is highly and positively correlated with the developed responsiveness construct, which significantly contributes to predicting Muslim tourists' future attitudes and intentions toward a destination. Furthermore, the moderating effect of the overall halal-friendly destination image is evaluated in a conceptual model (H. Han et al., 2020). Research findings (Sodawan, 2022) reveal the impact of halal-friendly attributes on perceived value and destination trust, and the mediating role of perceived value and destination trust in the relationship between environmental factors, namely halal-friendly attributes, and visit intentions in non-Muslim countries. Another study, conducted by Sirait & Rr. Diah Astarini (2024), showed a negative effect of online reviews on perceived risk, a negative effect of perceived risk on behavioral intentions, no effect of online reviews on behavioral intentions, and perceived risk mediating the effect of online reviews on behavioral intentions.

Research by Abror (2019) indicates that halal tourism and customer engagement significantly impact tourist satisfaction. Religiosity is a significant moderating variable in this relationship. Thus, this study contributes to the tourism sector, especially in halal tourism, religiosity, and customer satisfaction.

Halal destination attributes including halal social environment also received attention from researchers Dasangga & Ratnasari (2022) and the results were Halal destination attributes including halal social environment, facilities, food and beverages, services and local residents and staff positively and significantly influence destination attractiveness. But different research results are there is no relationship between visitor loyalty and destination image or destination image with destination trust. However, destination image has a significant effect on visitor satisfaction.

In addition, visitor experience has a positive effect on satisfaction and loyalty, while destination trust and destination attachment are positively related, Omo-Obas & Anning-Dorson (2023). What needs to be considered is that trust is a consequence of destination reputation, as well as tourists' cognitive and affective evaluations, Marinao Artigas et al., (2017), Enrique Marinao et al., (2017).

Research on tourist trust has been conducted by Ika Barokah Suryaningsiha et al. (2020). Their results showed that customer experience and destination image influence tourist satisfaction. Tourist experience has no significant effect on tourist trust, but destination image does influence tourist trust, and conversely, tourist satisfaction influences tourist trust. Another study by Dewi N. & Luki Adiati Pratomo (2023) found that visit intention can be achieved by increasing halal awareness, destination image, and destination trust. Research on revisit intention was also conducted by Supriono et al. (2023), which found that objective and constructive authenticity have a positive and significant effect on tourist experience. Meanwhile, tourist experience has a positive and significant effect on revisit intention. The mediating role of tourist experience also has a positive and significant effect.

R.A. Aliyah Khairunnisa et al. (2023) conducted research on destination trust using tourist experience. The results showed that tourist experience has a positive and significant effect on destination trust, a positive and significant effect on satisfaction, and revisit intention is also influenced by tourist experience.

HYPOTHESIS

H₁: There is an influence of Halal Destination Image on Trust Destination at halal tourist attractions in West Java Province.

H₂: There is an influence of Tourist Experience on Trust Destination at halal tourist attractions in West Java Province.

H₃: There is an influence of Service Quality on Trust Destination at halal tourist attractions in West Java Province.

- H₄: Halal Destination Image has an influence on Revisit Intention to halal tourist attractions in West Java Province.
- H₅: Tourist Experience has an influence on Revisit Intention at halal tourist attractions in West Java Province
- H₆: Service Quality has an influence on Revisit Intention at halal tourism objects in West Java Province.
- H₇: Trust Destination has an influence on Revisit Intention at halal tourism objects in West Java Province.

- HDI = Halal Destination Imaga
 TE = Tourist Experience
 SQ = Service Quality
 TD = Trust Destination
 RI = Revisit Intention

Figure 1: Research Framework Model

RESEARCH METHODS

This research is a descriptive field study using a quantitative approach to hypothesis testing. The research subjects were Generation Z tourists enrolled in Islamic Higher Education Institutions under the supervision of Kopertais Region 2 West Java and who had visited several halal tourism destinations in West Java in 2024, serving as the primary data source. The population consisted of 451,624 Generation Z tourists.

Furthermore, the researcher used a probability sampling technique to determine sample members by selecting representatives from each group in the population, with the number adjusted to the number of subjects in each group.

To determine the minimum sample size, if the population size is known, the Slovin formula can be used, assuming a tolerable sampling error of 5% (Sugiono, 2016):

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where:

n = sample size

N = population of 451,624

e = sampling error rate of 5%.

The results of the sample size calculation are as follows:

$$n = \frac{451.624}{1 + 451.624(5\%)^2} = \frac{451.624}{1 + 1.130,06} = \frac{451.624}{1.131,06} = 399,29 \sim 400 \text{ people}$$

Operational Variables:

Table 1: Operational Variables

Variable Notation	Conceptual Variables	Dimensions	Indicator	Indicator Code
Halal Destination image (HD) (ξ_1)	Halal destination image refers to an individual's mental representation (or interactive concept) of an individual's or group's knowledge, feelings, prejudices, imagination, emotional thoughts and overall perception of a particular destination purchased by tourists in accordance with halal standards that impact on their decision to visit.	Islamic Facilities (X1)	1. Availability of a Mosque. 2. Qibla Direction. 3. Ablution Facilities. 4. Safe Destination. 5. Captivating Tourist Attractions.	HD1-HD5
		Halal (X2)	6. Halal Kitchen Facilities 7. Halal Food Equipment 8. Halal Food 9. Good Halal Destinations	HD6-HD9
		Islamic Morals (X3)	10. Management Wears Syaria-compliant Clothing 11. Prostitution is prohibited 12. Sexual scenes are censored on TV 13. Providing a much-needed vacation according to Islamic law 14. Helping tourists escape from their daily routine according to Islamic law 15. Providing a different kind of excitement	HD10-HD15
		Drink (X4)	16. No alcoholic beverages are available 17. No gambling activities	HD16-HD19

Variable Notation	Conceptual Variables	Dimensions	Indicator	Indicator Code
Tourist Experience (TE) / (ξ ₂)	Tourist experience is a condition when tourists perceive subjectively and psychologically sensations or experiences resulting from interacting with service providers and other tourists automatically in their memory.		18. Written regulations regarding alcoholic beverages are in place 19. Free from gambling activities	
		Information (X5)	20. Information about halal facilities is available at tourist attractions. 21. Local staff are very knowledgeable about halal products and services.	HD20- HD21
		Atmosphere (X6)	22. The atmosphere of the tourist spot complies with Islamic law.	HD22
		Attractions (X7)	23. Historical and cultural attractions do not conflict with Islamic Syaria.	HD23
		Hedonism feeling of giving pleasure (X8)	1. I was very happy to have a new experience at the West Java destination. 2. I took part in activities during the trip. 3. I really enjoyed the trip. 4. I had an interesting experience.	TE1-TE4
		Novelty seeking novelty or new experiences (X9)	5. I had a unique experience 6. I had a once-in-a-lifetime experience 7. My trip to Jaipur was different from previous trips. 8. I experienced something new (e.g., food, activities, etc.) during my trip	TE5-TE8
		Local culture interacts with local communities to learn about their culture (X10)	9. I had a unique experience 10. I had a once-in-a-lifetime experience 11. My trip to Jaipur was different from previous trips 12. I experienced something new (e.g., food, activities, etc.) during my trip	TE9-TE12
Refreshment, freedom to relax (X11)	13. I de-stress during the trip 14. I feel free from my daily routine during the trip 15. I have a refreshing experience 16. I feel better after the trip	TE13- TE16		
Meaningfulness of profound or significant experiences (X12)	17. I de-stress during the trip 18. I feel free from my daily routine during the trip 19. I have a refreshing experience 20. I feel better after the trip	TE17- TE20		
Involvement level of	21. I had a unique experience	TE21- TE24		

Variable Notation	Conceptual Variables	Dimensions	Indicator	Indicator Code
		involvement with on-site activities (X13)	22. I had a once-in-a-lifetime experience 23. My trip to Jaipur was different from previous trips 24. I experienced something new (e.g., food, activities, etc.) during my trip	
		Knowledge information about a site (X14)	25. I gained a lot of information during my trip 26. I gained new skills from this trip 27. I experienced a new culture	TE25-TE27
		Adverse feelings, when operationalized, captures negative emotions. (X15)	28. I was angry during my stay 29. I was frustrated during my stay 30. I felt embarrassed during my stay	TE28-TE30
Service Quality (SQ) / (ξ3)	Service quality in this research is a measure or scale for companies that shows whether the company has been able to meet tourist expectations with the service performance they provide.	Tangible (X16)	1. Modern and technologically advanced vehicles are available. 2. Tangibility: The infrastructure is well-designed and of excellent quality. 3. The food offered is of exceptional quality. 4. The accommodations and facilities are attractive and well-designed. 5. The motel I stayed at and the tour guide's appearance were neat and clean.	SQ1-SQ5
		Empathy (X17)	6. The service was provided by pleasant and friendly staff. 7. My special requirements and exceptions were handled as planned. 8. Personal safety was considered a key factor in all services provided.	SQ6-SQ8
		Responsiveness (X18)	9. The staff genuinely wanted to solve the problem. 10. The staff provided sufficient and clear information about the services they provide. 11. The staff fulfilled my requests quickly and efficiently. 12. The staff provided me with detailed information about available entertainment.	SQ9-SQ14

Variable Notation	Conceptual Variables	Dimensions	Indicator	Indicator Code
			13. The staff showed a genuine desire and interest in supporting and assisting me. 14. The staff advised me on how to make the most of my free time.	
		Reliability (X19)	15. The service provided was accurate from the start. 16. The traveler received the service as promised. 17. The scheduled tour was completed as planned. 18. During my stay at the destination, there were no issues with the service.	SQ15-SQ18
		Assurance (X20)	19. During my trip to the tourist destination, I received excellent customer service from knowledgeable staff. 20. The level of service excellence increased my confidence in the services offered during my visit to Meghalaya. 21. To make my stay more comfortable, I was provided with thorough, professional, and competent tour and hotel assistance. 22. The staff spoke to me fluently and in a manner I could understand.	SQ19-SQ22
Destinati on Trust (DT)/(η1)	Destination trust is a condition where tourists find a match (relevance) with what they think, including getting a good overall impression of the tourist destination, which is reliable, transparent, risk-free and in accordance with what the marketer advertises, which will then be used as a basis for returning.	Fulfilling expectations (Y1)	1. Meets Traveler Expectations 2. Travel providers provide accurate information	DT1-DT2
		Feel confident (Y2)	3. Travelers feel confident 4. Halal Travel Providers are reliable signage.	DT3-DT4
		Not disappointing (Y3)	5. Travelers will never be disappointed with the service. 6. A destination that never disappoints me	DT5-DT6
		Guarantee satisfaction (Y4)	7. Destinations guarantee tourist satisfaction 8. Efforts to satisfy	DT7-DT8
		Able to overcome desires (Y5)	9. Honest Destination Managers 10. Sincere Destination Managers 11. Halal travel providers do not make false claims about their products.	DT9-DT11

Variable Notation	Conceptual Variables	Dimensions	Indicator	Indicator Code
		Reliable (Y6)	12. Destination can be relied upon 13. Destination can solve problems	DT12- DT13
		Provide compensation in the event of an accident (Y7)	14. Provide compensation to tourists if they experience injuries after serving	DT14
		Inhabitants (Y8)	15. The people here are honest. 16. The people here are concerned about the well-being of tourists. 17. The people here are skilled at dealing with tourists.	DT15- DT17
		Public Institution (Y9)	18. Public institutions in this place are reliable. 19. Public institutions in this place operate in the interests of tourists. 20. Public institutions in this place carry out their duties well.	DT18- DT20
Revisit Intention (RI) _(η²)	Revisit intention is the level of intention to return to the same destination or as post-visit behavior, namely the willingness to re-explore the same destination or the intention to revisit a halal tourist destination as a positive behavioral intention of customers to re-explore halal tourist destinations in the future, because it is influenced by behavior based on past tourist experiences and satisfaction, namely the positive influence of word of mouth, recommendations, and repeat purchases, indicating the customer's desire to reuse the product.	Willingness of tourists to return. (Z1)	1. Visit again 2. Plan to visit 3. Wish to visit again	RI1-RI3
		Willingness of tourists to provide recommendations (Z2)	4. Willingness to introduce the place to other people 5. Spread positive news about the place	RI4-RI5
		The willingness of tourists to provide a perceived experience. (Z3)	6. Recommend this trip to others based on a positive experience 7. Advise people to visit this location	RI6-RI7
		The willingness of tourists to set a destination as a priority (Z4)	8. Want to visit more often 9. Tourists witness the potential for this destination to become famous 10. Become a priority Muslim-friendly tourist destination	RI8-RI10

RESEARCH RESULTS

A. Analysis of Research Variable Description

Table 2: Range and Category Values

Score Interval	Halal Destination Image	Tourist Experience	Service Quality	Destination Trust	Revisit Intention
1,00-1,80	Very bad	Very Low	Very Low	Very Low	Very Low
1,81-2,60	Bad	Low	Low	Low	Low
2,61-3,40	Fairly Good	High enough	High enough	High enough	High enough
3,41-4,20	Good	High	High	High	High
4,21-5,00	Very Good	Very high	Very high	Very high	Very high

Source: Zikmund, William G., et. al (2019)

Table 3: Hybrid Model Measurement Model Suitability – SEM

Goodness of Fit Indicator	Expected Size	Estimation Results	Conclusion
Absolute Fit Size			
<i>Goodness of Fit Index (GFI)</i>	GFI > 0,90	0,87	Marginal Fit
<i>Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA)</i>	RMSEA < 0,08	0,077	Good Fit
Incremental Fit Size			
<i>Non-Normed Fit Index (NNFI)</i>	NNFI > 0,90	0,93	Good Fit
<i>Normed Fit Index (NFI)</i>	NFI > 0,90	0,91	Good Fit
<i>Adjusted Goodness of Fit Index (AGFI)</i>	AGFI > 0,90	0,81	Marginal Fit
<i>Relative Fit Index (RFI)</i>	RFI > 0,90	0,88	Marginal Fit
<i>Incremental Fit Index (IFI)</i>	IFI > 0,90	0,94	Good Fit
<i>Comparative Fit Index (CFI)</i>	CFI > 0,90	0,94	Good Fit

Source: Processed data

Table 4: Hybrid Model Measurement Analysis (Full Model)

Measurement Model		SLF	STD. Error (SE)	t value	Construct Reliability (CR)	Extract Variance (VE)
Latent Variables	Manifest Variables					
Halal Destination Image (HD)	Islamic Facilities (X1)	0.52	0.070	7.42	0.976	0.858
	Halal (X2)	0.67	0.068	9.91		
	Islamic Morals (X3)	0.68	0.067	10.16		
	Drinks (X4)	0.69	0.065	10.58		
	Information (X5)	0.80	0.062	12.89		
	Atmosphere (X6)	0.51	0.074	6.86		
	Attractions (X7)	0.56	0.069	8.17		
Tourist Experience (TE)	Hedonism) (X8)	0.67	0.068	9.89	0.981	0.867
	Novelty) (X9)	0.56	0.067	8.42		
	Local culture (X10)	0.56	0.067	8.36		
	Refreshment (X11)	0.62	0.065	9.59		
	Meaningfulness (X12)	0.81	0.065	12.52		
	Involvement (X13)	0.66	0.064	10.29		
	Knowledge (X14)	0.65	0.070	9.24		

Measurement Model		SLF	STD. Error (SE)	t value	Construct Reliability (CR)	Extract Variance (VE)
Latent Variables	Manifest Variables					
	Adverse feelings (X15)	0.68	0.064	10.57		
Service Quality (SQ)	Tangible (X16)	0.51	0.077	6.59	0.966	0.855
	Empathy (X17)	0.81	0.060	13.44		
	Responsiveness (X18)	0.77	0.060	12.77		
	Reliability (X19)	0.56	0.085	6.62		
	Assurance (X20)	0.50	0.070	7.17		
Destination Trust (DT)	Meets expectations (Y1)	0.77	0.177	4.35	0.959	0.729
	Feels confident (Y2)	0.55	0.127	4.34		
	Does not disappoint (Y3)	0.50	0.130	3.84		
	Guarantees satisfaction (Y4)	0.78	0.182	4.29		
	Able to meet expectations (Y5)	0.70	0.166	4.22		
	Reliable (Y6)	0.67	0.160	4.19		
	Provides compensation in the event of an accident (Y7)	0.60	0.146	4.11		
	Inhabitants (Y8)	0.53	0.136	3.91		
Public Institution (Y9)	0.51	0.116	4.41			
Revisit Intention (RI)	Tourist willingness to revisit (Z1)	0.88	0.060	14.65	0.969	0.889
	Tourist willingness to provide recommendations (Z2)	0.72	0.065	11.15		
	Tourist willingness to share their experiences (Z3)	0.61	0.067	9.17		
	Tourist willingness to prioritize a destination (Z4)	0.61	0.064	9.54		

Source: Processed data

Table 5: Summary of Test Results Between Latent Variables

No	Jalur Struktural	Path Coefficient	t-Value	t-kriteria	Test Results
1	Halal Destination Image → Destination Trust	0.30	3.89	1.96	Significant
2	Tourist Experience → Destination Trust	0.41	6.34	1.96	Significant
3	Service Quality → Destination Trust	0.35	4.35	1.96	Significant
4	Halal Destination Image → Revisit Intention	0.21	2.19	1.96	Significant
5	Tourist Experience → Revisit Intention	0.18	2.04	1.96	Significant
6	Service Quality → Revisit Intention	0.33	4.04	1.96	Significant
7	Destination Trust → Revisit Intention	0,39	5.84	1.96	Significant

Source: Processed data

Sub-Structural Equation 1

$$DT = 0.30*HD + 0.41*TE + 0.35*SQ, \text{ Errorvar.} = 0.26, R^2 = 0.74$$

$$\begin{matrix} (0.077) & (0.064) & (0.08) & (0.085) \\ 3.89 & 6.34 & 4.35 & 2.95 \end{matrix}$$

Sub-Structural Equation 2

$$RI = 0.39*DT + 0.21*HD + 0.18*TE + 0.33*SQ, \text{ Errorvar.} = 0.11, R^2 = 0.89$$

(0.067)	(0.096)	(0.088)	(0.082)	(0.054)
5.84	2.19	2.04	4.04	2.02

Figure 2: Hybrid Model (Full SEM) Standardized

Figure 3: Hybrid Model (Full SEM) t-Value

Table 11: Hypothesis Test Results

Hypothesis		Hypothesis Statement	Path Coef. /R ²	t value	t criteria	Test Results
H1	H ₀	Halal Destination Image Does Not Affect Destination Trust	0.30	3.89	1.96	H ₀ is rejected and H _a is accepted. Halal Destination Image Affects Destination Trust
	H _a	Halal Destination Image Affects Destination Trust				
H2	H ₀	Tourist Experience Does Not Influence Destination Trust	0.41	6.34	1.96	H ₀ is rejected and H _a is accepted Tourist Experience Influences Destination Trust
	H _a	Tourist Experience Influences Destination Trust				
H3	H ₀	Service Quality has no effect on Destination Trust	0.35	4.35	1.96	H ₀ is rejected and H _a is accepted. Service Quality has an effect on Destination Trust
	H _a	Service Quality has an effect on Destination Trust				
H4	H ₀	Halal Destination Image Does Not Influence Revisit Intention	0.21	2.19	1.96	H ₀ is rejected and H _a is accepted. Halal Destination Image Influences Revisit Intention
	H _a	Halal Destination Image Influences Revisit Intention				
H5	H ₀	Tourist Experience has no effect on Revisit Intention	0.18	2.04	1.96	H ₀ is rejected and H _a is accepted. Tourist Experience has an effect on Revisit Intention
	H _a	Tourist Experience has an effect on Revisit Intention				
H6	H ₀	Service Quality Has No Effect on Revisit Intention	0.33	4.04	1.96	H ₀ is rejected and H _a is accepted Service Quality Has an Effect on Revisit Intention
	H _a	Service Quality Has an Effect on Revisit Intention				
H7	H ₀	Destination Trust Does Not Influence Revisit Intention	0.39	5.84	1.96	H ₀ is rejected and H _a is accepted Destination Trust Influences Revisit Intention
	H _a	Destination Trust Influences Revisit Intention				

Source: Processed data

H₁: Halal Destination Image significantly influences Destination Trust at halal tourist attractions in West Java Province.

H₂: Tourist Experience significantly influences Destination Trust at halal tourist attractions in West Java Province.

H₃: Service Quality significantly influences Destination Trust at halal tourist attractions in West Java Province.

H₄: Halal Destination Image significantly influences Revisit Intention at halal tourist attractions in West Java Province.

H₅: Tourist Experience significantly influences Revisit Intention at halal tourist attractions in West Java Province.

H₆: Service Quality significantly influences Revisit Intention at halal tourist attractions in West Java Province.

H₇: Destination Trust significantly influences Revisit Intention at halal tourist attractions in West Java Province.

DISCUSSION

The Halal Destination Image variable used in this study positively impacts Destination Trust. Similar results were also found for Tourist Experience and Service Quality, each of which positively impacted Destination Trust. Therefore, a systematic process of collecting, analyzing, and strategically distributing information about Halal destination image, tourist experience, service quality, and future tourism industry trends should be used by companies to make better business decisions, taking into account the exogenous variables used in this study. These considerations are necessary to anticipate changes in market conditions, identify opportunities and threats, and ultimately achieve a competitive advantage. Regarding these factors, this study found a very positive impact on destination trust and revisit intention. However, the dominant influence of tourist experience on destination trust and destination trust on revisit intention requires special attention.

CONCLUSION

Findings: Tourist Experience is the dominant variable for the Trust Destination variable at halal tourist attractions in West Java Province, where the Trust Destination variable can successfully mediate or explain its influence on the research problem, namely Revisit Intention at halal tourist attractions in West Java Province..

Acknowledgments

Thanks to colleagues who have helped in conducting this research. Hopefully in the future we can conduct research with the ideas needed by the people in need

Bibliography

- 1) Abror, A., Patrisia, D., Engriani, Y., Omar, M. W., Wardi, Y., Noor, N. M. B. M., Sabir Ahmad, S. S., & Najib, M. (2022). Perceived risk and tourist's trust: the roles of perceived value and religiosity. *Journal of Islamic Marketing*, 13(12), 2742–2758. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JIMA-03-2021-0094>
- 2) Afandi, M. F., Adove, D. A., & Destari, F. (2024). The Effect of eWOM Social Media on Purchase Intention: The Role Moderation of Involvement. *KnE Social Sciences*, 2024, 181–193. <https://doi.org/10.18502/kss.v9i10.15724>
- 3) Afshardoost, M., & Eshaghi, M. S. (2020). Destination image and tourist behavioural intentions: A meta-analysis. *Tourism Management*. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0261517720300789>
- 4) Ahyani, H., Huda, M., & Hamzah, I. (2023). Maqasid Syariah Pariwisata Halal : Analysis of the Principles of Islamic Law, Islamic Economic Ethics, Islamic Business Ethics, and Islamic Service Ethics in Optimizing Halal Tourism Potential from the Perspective of Islamic Legal Philosophy. *Widina Media Utama*. <https://repository.penerbitwidina.com/media/publications/565663-maqashid-syariah-pariwisata-halal-analis-56486b87>.

- 5) Aldrian, Suhud, U., & Febrilia, I. (2022). The Influence of Electronic Word of Mouth, Destination Image, Attitude Toward Destination and Destination Trust on Visit Intention: A Study on Generation Z in Jabotabek. *Jurnal Bisnis, Manajemen Dan Keuangan*, 3(8.5.2017), 502–517.
- 6) Amalia, F. A., & Gunawan, A. I. (2023). Livening up Japan’s halal tourism by captivating Indonesian potential Muslim tourists. *Journal of Islamic Marketing*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JIMA-04-2022-0106>
- 7) Amin, M., Idrus, Y., Puturu, D., & Said Perintah, S. (2023), The Influence of Tourism Object Development and Tourist Visit Rates on Community Economic Growth, *Journal of Business Application | Mei*, 2, 16–29.
- 8) Andriani, N., & Kurriwati, N. (2022). The role of experiential marketing, destination brand image, and halal tourism products on tourists’ revisit decision in halal tourism village. In *Contemporary Research on Management and Business* (pp. 172–175). CRC Press. <https://doi.org/10.1201/9781003295952-44>
- 9) Asri, S. K., & Julisman, I. (2022). The Influence of Philips Brand Image and Product Quality on Consumer Purchase Interest at Yogya Garnd Majalengka, *Jurnal Impresi Indonesia*, 1(3), 282–287. <https://doi.org/10.36418/jii.v1i3.40>
- 10) Asy’ari, R., Tahir, R., Rakhman, C. U., & Putra, R. R. (2021), Community-Based Tourism Development in West Java Province, *Journal of Sociology Research and Education*, 8(1), 47. <https://doi.org/10.24036/scs.v8i1.292>
- 11) Athar, H. S., Mulyono, L. E. H., & Sutanto, H. (2020), The Influence of Customer Experiences on Domestic Tourist Satisfaction: The Mediating Role of Halal Destination Image, *Altasia: Jurnal Pariwisata Indonesia*, 2(2), 107–116. <https://doi.org/10.37253/altasia.v2i2.552>
- 12) Auriza, M. Z., Putra, S. M., & Nugraha, M. E. (2024). Exploring Destination Uniqueness : Unraveling Revisit Intentions Through Enhanced Tourist Experiences. 3(1), 171–186. <https://doi.org/10.55299/ijec.v3i1.687>
- 13) Bailey, A. E. (2022). *International Journal of Religious Tourism and Pilgrimage*. *International Journal of Religious Tourism and Pilgrimage*, 4(2), 189–202. <https://www.academia.edu/download/83939416/viewcontent.pdf>
- 14) Bundawi, D., Arief, R. F., & Ariyanto, H. H. (2022), The Influence of Revisit Intention Mediated by Satisfaction on Fast Food in Sanctuary Batam, *Jesya*, 5(2), 1585–1597. <https://doi.org/10.36778/jesya.v5i2.768>
- 15) Chairunisa, S., & Dwiyanto, B. M. (2023), The Influence of Service Quality, Experiential Marketing, and Destination Image on the Decision to Revisit Through Visitor Satisfaction as an Intervening Variable (A Study on the Religious Tourism Object of the Great Mosque of Banten), <https://repofeb.undip.ac.id/id/eprint/12328>
- 16) Cui, M., Cheng, L., & Shang, Y. (2024). The influence of experiencescape of home-based accommodation on tourists’ subjective well-being at cultural heritage sites: The role of value co-creation. *Journal of Destination Marketing and Management*, 31(November 2023), 100845. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jdmm.2023.100845>
- 17) Dewi, N., & Luki Adiati Pratomo. (2023). Effect Of Halal Awareness, Destination Image, And Destination Trust On Visit Intention. *Jurnal Ekonomi Trisakti*, 3(1), 1045–1056. <https://doi.org/10.25105/jet.v3i1.16037>
- 18) Dewi, N., & Pratomo, L. (2023). Effect Of Halal Awareness, Destination Image, And Destination Trust On Visit Intention. *Jurnal Ekonomi Trisakti*, 3, 1045–1056. <https://doi.org/10.25105/jet.v3i1.16037>
- 19) Evren, S., Şimşek Evren, E., & Çakıcı, A. C. (2020). Moderating effect of optimum stimulation level on the relationship between satisfaction and revisit intention: the case of Turkish cultural tourists. *International Journal of Culture, Tourism, and Hospitality Research*, 14(4), 681–695. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJCTHR-03-2019-0052>

- 20) Faishal Burhanudin, M., & Yusuf, A. (2023), The Influence of Co-Creative Tourism Experience on Revisit Intention of Karawang Culinary, *Jurnal Perspektif*, 21(2), 143–152. <https://doi.org/10.31294/jp.v21i2.16606>
- 21) Farizkhan, M. M., Masnita, Y., & Chrisjatmiko, K. (2023). Halal Tourism in Theory of Planned Behavior: Intention to Recommend Variable Analysis. *Journal of Social Research*, 2(8), 2592–2599. <https://doi.org/10.55324/josr.v2i8.1308>
- 22) Fatmawati, Fortuna, H., Siburian, B., & Ilhami, A. (2023), Halal Tourism Destination Development in Multiethnic and Multireligious Regions: A Case Study of Asian Heritage Tourist Attractions, *Jurnal Industri Pariwisata*, 6(1), 41–49. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tmp.2015.12.014>
- 23) Febrianty, D. S., & Rulindo, R. (2024), Factors Influencing Intention to Visit Halal Tourism Areas in Indonesia: A Theory of Planned Behavior Approach, *Journal of Economic, Bussines and Accounting (Costing)*, 7(2), 3307–3321. <https://doi.org/10.31539/costing.v7i2.7254>
- 24) Firmansyah, D., & Dede. (2022), Common Sampling Techniques in Research Methodology: Literature Review, *Jurnal Ilmiah Pendidikan Holistik (JIPH)*, 1(2), 85–114. <https://doi.org/10.55927/jiph.v1i2.937>
- 25) Han, H. (2021). Consumer behavior and environmental sustainability in tourism and hospitality: a review of theories, concepts, and latest research. *Journal of Sustainable Tourism*, 29(7), 1021–1042. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09669582.2021.1903019>
- 26) Han, H., Al-Ansi, A., Chua, B.-L., Tariq, B., Radic, A., & Park, S. (2020). The Post-Coronavirus World in the International Tourism Industry: Application of the Theory of Planned Behavior to Safer Destination Choices in the Case of US Outbound Tourism. In *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* (Vol. 17, Issue 18, p. 6485). MDPI AG. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17186485>
- 27) Han, J., Zuo, Y., Law, R., Chen, S., & Zhang, M. (2021). Service quality in tourism public health: trust, satisfaction, and loyalty. In *Frontiers in psychology*. [frontiersin.org. https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.731279](https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.731279)
- 28) Hariani, D., & Hanafiah, M. H. (2023). The competitiveness, challenges and opportunities to accommodate the Halal tourism market: a Sharia-law tourism destination perspectives. *Journal of Islamic Marketing*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JIMA-05-2023-0147>
- 29) Hasan, A. A. T. (2024). Factors influencing halal tourism destinations revisit intentions among Muslim travelers of Bangladesh: the mediating role of emotional attachments. *Journal of Islamic Marketing*, 15(3), 720–744. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JIMA-02-2023-0045>
- 30) Hasan, H. A. (2022), Halal Tourism: Challenges and Opportunities in the New Normal Era, *Jurnal Kajian Islam Kontemporer*, 13(1), 54–66. <https://journal.unismuh.ac.id/index.php/pilar/article/download/7946/4823>
- 31) Hassan, S. B., & Soliman, M. (2021). COVID-19 and repeat visitation: Assessing the role of destination social responsibility, destination reputation, holidaymakers' trust and fear arousal. *Journal of Destination Marketing and Management*, 19(May 2020). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jdmm.2020.100495>
- 32) Herman, L. E., Athar, H. S., & Dakwah, M. M. (2024). The Effect of Halal Destination Image and Tourist Motivation on Revisit Intention: The Role of Halal Experience Satisfaction. *Amwaluna: Jurnal Ekonomi Dan Keuangan Syariah*, 8(1), 113–123. <https://doi.org/10.29313/amwaluna.v8i1.3471>
- 33) Hermina, U. N. (2020). Marketing Strategy To Increase Tourist Visits on Nature Tourism of Mempawah Mangrove Park in the Pasir Village of Mempawah Regency. *Jurnal Terapan Manajemen Dan Bisnis*, 5(2), 51. <https://doi.org/10.26737/jtmb.v5i2.1772>
- 34) Hidayat, N. K., Bustaman, Y., & Hartono, Y. H. (2020). The Influence of Service Quality on Customer Trust. *7(1)*, 320–327. <https://doi.org/10.2991/aebmr.k.201222.037>

- 35) Irsyadi, N. A., & Andriani, N. (2024), The Influence of Tourist Experience on Return Visit Intention Through Customer Satisfaction Mediation at Sembilan Beach, Gili Gending District, Sumenep Regency, *Management Studies and Entrepreneurship Journal*, 5(1), 308–319. <http://journal.yrpiiku.com/index.php/msej>
- 36) Ismadi, I., & Suwitho, S. (2024). the Effect of Tourism Attraction and Tourist Experience on Revisit Intention Mediated By Tourist Satisfaction (a Study At Mount Bromo Tourist Destination, East Java). *International Conference of Business and Social Sciences*, 3(1), 474–486. <https://doi.org/10.24034/icobuss.v3i1.401>
- 37) Jawa-Barat, D. P. dan K. P. (2024), Implementation of Muslim-Friendly Natural Tourism Attraction Standards for West Java in 2024, West Java Provincial Tourism and Culture Office, https://drive.google.com/file/d/1dTScfvRkHrAEKQ_DoIX6ZfUyXnMLRQp/view
- 38) Julina, Asnawi, A., & Sihombing, P. R. (2021). The Antecedent of Intention to Visit Halal Tourism Areas Using the Theory of Planned Behavior: The Moderating Effect of Religiosity. *Journal of Tourism Management Research*, 8(2), 127–135. <https://doi.org/10.18488/journal.31.2021.82.127.135>
- 39) Khairunnisal, R. . A., Suhud, U., & Sari, D. A. P. (2023), The Influence of Tourist Experience on Trust, Satisfaction and Perceived Value for Revisit Intention, *Humantech Jurnal Ilmiah Multi Disiplin Indonesia*, 2(12), 2546–2557.
- 40) Králiková, A., Peruthová, A., & Ryglová, K. (2020). Impact of destination image on satisfaction and loyalty. *Acta Universitatis Agriculturae et Silviculturae Mendelianae Brunensis*, 68(1), 199–209. <https://doi.org/10.11118/actaun202068010199>
- 41) Kurniawan, A., Sukardi, S., Indrasti, N. S., & Suparno, O. (2021), Analysis of the Sustainability Potential of the Leather Tanning Industry with an Interest-Based Loan Capital Structure, *Jurnal Teknologi Industri Pertanian*, 15(4), 1038–1045. <https://doi.org/10.21107/agrointek.v15i4.9308>
- 42) Kurniawan, D. T., et., al. (2024). The Effect of Destination Image, Memorable Tourism Experiences, e-WOM, and Brand Trust on Revisit Intention in Trenggalek, East Java Indonesia (Vol. 1). Atlantis Press International BV. https://doi.org/10.2991/978-94-6463-204-0_63
- 43) Kurniawan, R., & Hanifah, R. D. (2023), The Influence of Facilities on Revisit Intention with Guest Satisfaction as an Intervening Variable (Case Study: Novotel Jakarta Gajah Mada), *Ultima Management : Jurnal Ilmu Manajemen*, 15(1), 131–146. <https://doi.org/10.31937/manajemen.v15i1.3200>
- 44) Kusumawardani, N. (2020), The Influence of Destination Image and Tourist Attraction on Revisit Intention with Satisfaction as an Intervening Variable (A Study on Climbers of Mount Prau via Patak Banteng), *Jurnal Ekonomi*, 1–13.
- 45) Lan, M. T. K., & Hoàng, T. H. (2021). The Influence Of Destination Social Responsibility On Revisit Intentions Of Tourists: A Case Study In Da Lat. *Hue University Journal of Science: Economics and Development*, 130(5A). <https://doi.org/10.26459/hueunijed.v130i5a.6307>
- 46) Mansur, A., & Ridwan, R. (2022), Characteristics of generation Z students and the need for development in the field of guidance and counseling., 17(1), 120–130. <https://doi.org/10.29408/edc.v17i1.5922>
- 47) Marinao Artigas, E., et., al. (2017a), Determinants of trust towards tourist destinations, *Journal of Destination Marketing and Management*, 6(4), 327–334. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jdmm.2017.03.003>
- 48) Marinao Artigas, E., et., al. (2017b). Determinants of trust towards tourist destinations. *Journal of Destination Marketing and Management*, 6(4), 327–334. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jdmm.2017.03.003>
- 49) Monoarfa, H., et., al. (2023), Halal awareness can't improved purchase intention imported skincare, *Al-Uqud : Journal of Islamic Economics*, 7(1), 54–66. <https://doi.org/10.26740/aluqud.v7n1.p54-66>
- 50) Nguyen Viet, B., Dang, H. P., & Nguyen, H. H. (2020), Revisit intention and satisfaction: The role of destination image, perceived risk, and cultural contact, *Cogent Business and Management*, 7(1), <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311975.2020.1796249>

- 51) Omo-Obas, P., & Anning-Dorson, T. (2023), Cognitive-affective-motivation factors influencing international visitors' destination satisfaction and loyalty, *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Insights*, 6(5), 2222–2240, <https://doi.org/10.1108/JHTI-05-2022-0178>
- 52) Permana, D., & Humairah, D. (2022). Recognizing The Halal Tourism Destination in Indonesia from the Lens of Destination Image, E-Wom and Muslim-Friendly Amenities. *International Journal of Scientific Research in Science and Technology*, 615–624. <https://doi.org/10.32628/ijrst229376>
- 53) Pohan, M., & Novien Rialdy. (2024), Analysis of Factors Influencing Gen Z Behavior in Determining Which Businesses They Are Interested in as Small Businesses, *Jurnal Ilmiah Ekonomi Dan Manajemen*, 2(6), 295–302. <https://doi.org/10.61722/jiem.v2i6.1430>
- 54) Prakos Pranindyasari, C., et., al. (2023), Risk Perception Analysis of Travel Intentions and Covid-19 Testing Requirements in Indonesia, *Jurnal Manajemen Perhotelan Dan Pariwisata*, 6(2), 451–460. <https://doi.org/10.23887/jmpp.v6i2.60244>
- 55) Prasanthi Ni Putu Pebri, N. W. N. B. (2022), The effect of marketing mix, price and customer experience on customer satisfaction at Banyuasri Singaraja Market influence. *Costing, Journal of Economic, Business and Accounting Volume*, 6(1).
- 56) Qadri, R. A. (2022). Word of Mouth and Quality Services; Their Impact on Destination Trust and Revisit Intention on in the Riau Islands' Destination. *Journal of Business Studies and Mangement Review*, 6(1), 64–69. <https://doi.org/10.22437/jbsmr.v6i1.21403>
- 57) Rakhmad, A. A. N., et., al. (2022). A User-Centered Design (UCD) approach to designing and building halal tourism application to advance halal tourism in East Java. In *Reinforcement of the Halal Industry for Global Integration Revival* (pp. 36–42). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.1201/9781003324492-6>
- 58) Ramadhanti, D., & Marsasi, E. G. (2023a). The Influence of Attitudes and Halal Perceptions on Intention to Visit Halal Tourism Destinations. In *JESI (Jurnal Ekonomi Syariah Indonesia)* (Vol. 13, Issue 1, p. 54). Alma Ata University Press. [https://doi.org/10.21927/jesi.2023.13\(1\).54-73](https://doi.org/10.21927/jesi.2023.13(1).54-73)
- 59) Ramadhanti, D., & Marsasi, E. G. (2023b), The Influence of Attitudes and Halal Perceptions on Intention to Visit Halal Tourism Destinations. *JESI (Jurnal Ekonomi Syariah)*, <https://ejournal.almaata.ac.id/index.php/JESI/article/view/3088>
- 60) Rasoolimanesh, S. M., Seyfi, S., Rastegar, R., & Hall, C. M. (2021), Destination image during the COVID-19 pandemic and future travel behavior: The moderating role of past experience, *Journal of Destination Marketing and Management*, 21(February), 100620. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jdmm.2021.100620>
- 61) Rendiansyah, & Putra, H. T. (2024), The Influence of Service Quality and Price on Customer Loyalty with Customer Satisfaction as an Intervening Variable: Study of Indomaret in Bandung Raya, *Asian Journal of Economics, Business and Accounting*, 24(2), 14–28. <https://doi.org/10.9734/ajeba/2024/v24i21216>
- 62) Riansyah, A., & Ismail, N. (2024), The Influence of Halal Tourism Literacy Levels and Tourist Behavior on Interest in Halal Tourism in Riau Province, *Indonesian Journal of Islamic Economics and Business*, 9(1), 110–126. <https://doi.org/10.30631/ijoeib.v9i1.2284>
- 63) Rohman, F. (2021), Tourist Behavior Model for Spiritual Tourism Destinations: Application of Service Dominant Logic in the Tourism Industry, *Mix: Jurnal Ilmiah Manajemen*, 11(1), 107. <https://doi.org/10.22441/mix.2021.v11i1.008>
- 64) Rosi, F., & AS, F. (2024), The Role of Destination Image and E-WOM on Revisit Intention Through Visiting Decisions in Sampang Regency Tourism, *Jurnal Bina Manajemen*, 13(2), 64–82. <https://doi.org/10.52859/jbm.v13i2.545>

- 65) Roza, M., Agussalim, M., & Begawati, N. (2021), The Influence of Service Quality and Customer Satisfaction on Consumer Behavioral Intentions at Bagan Padang Restaurant, *Matua Jurnal (Development of Management and Business Science)*, 3(1), 151–166.
<https://garuda.kemdikbud.go.id/documents/detail/2280658>
- 66) Sekar Arum, L., Amira Zahrani, & Duha, N. A. (2023), Characteristics of Generation Z and Their Readiness to Face the 2030 Demographic Bonus, *Accounting Student Research Journal*, 2(1), 59–72.
<https://doi.org/10.62108/asrj.v2i1.5812>
- 67) Setiawan, A. (2022), Indonesia's Biodiversity: Problems and Conservation Efforts, *Indonesian Journal of Conservation*, 11(1), 13–21. <https://doi.org/10.15294/ijc.v11i1.34532>
- 68) Sirait, B. K., & Rr. Diah Astarini. (2024), Antecedents of Online Review of Behavioral Intentions Mediated by Perceived Risk, *Jurnal Ekonomi Trisakti*, 4(1), 395–404. <https://doi.org/10.25105/jet.v4i1.18951>
- 69) Soemadi, R.A. (2023), The Influence of Digital Marketing and Product Quality on Fried Chicken Home Delivery Purchase Decisions, *Jurnal Ekonomi Dan Manajemen*, 20(2), 189–197.
- 70) Srivastava, S., et., al. (2022), Impact of destination brand experience on destination advocacy: trust and loyalty as moderators, *Consumer Behavior in Tourism and Hospitality*, 17(4), 576–590.
<https://doi.org/10.1108/CBTH-01-2022-0002>
- 71) Supriono, Iqbal, M., Kusumawati, A., & Fahmi, M. R. A. (2023), The role of authenticity on revisit intention: tourist experience as a mediation at the Reyog Ponorogo National Festival, *International Journal of Event and Festival Management*, 14(3), 344–362. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJEFM-09-2022-0069>
- 72) Suriani, N., Risnita, & Jailani, M. S. (2023), The Concept of Population and Sampling and Participant Selection from the Perspective of Educational Scientific Research, *Jurnal IHSAN : Jurnal Pendidikan Islam*, 1(2), 24–36. <https://doi.org/10.61104/ihsan.v1i2.55>
- 73) Suryani, S., & Othman, L. (2022), The Influence of Service Quality on Consumer Satisfaction During the Covid-19 Pandemic at Stefani City Hotel Pekanbaru, *JOM FISIP Vol. 9: Edisi I Januari-Juni 2022*, 9(8.5.2017), 2003–2005. <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/autism-spectrum-disorders>
- 74) Suryaningsiha, et., al. (2020), Reflection of Customer Experience and Destination Image of Tourist Trust through Satisfaction Mediation, *Hasanuddin Economics and Business Review*, 4(1), 1.
<https://doi.org/10.26487/hebr.v4i1.2329>
- 75) Suryanto, & Kurniati, P. S. (2020), Tourism Development Strategy In Indonesia, *Academy of Strategic Management Journal*, 19(6), 1–8.
- 76) Torres-Moraga, E., et., al. (2024), Tourscape role in tourist destination sustainability: A path towards revisit, *Journal of Destination Marketing and Management*, 31(December 2023), 100863.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jdmm.2024.100863>
- 77) Widjaja, Y. I., Khalifa, G. S. A., & Abuelhassan, A. E. (2020). The effect of Islamic attributes and destination affective image on the reputation of the Halal tourism destination of Jakarta. *Journal of Environmental Management and Tourism*, 11(2), 299–313. [https://doi.org/10.14505/jemt.v11.2\(42\).08](https://doi.org/10.14505/jemt.v11.2(42).08)
- 78) Wufron, Rohimat Nurhasan, M. R. (2020), Value Co-Creation of Word of Mouth Through Customer Satisfaction, *Jurnal Wacana Ekonomi*, 20(01), 009–016.
- 79) Zaki, M., & Saiman, S. (2021), A Study on Statistical Hypothesis Formulation in Research Hypothesis Testing, *JIP - Jurnal Ilmiah Ilmu Pendidikan*, 4(2), 115–118. <https://doi.org/10.54371/jiip.v4i2.216>